

FIRST RECORD OF *OECOTHEA PRAECOX* (LOEW, 1862) (DIPTERA, HELEOMYZIDAE) FROM SLOVAKIA

PIERWSZE STWIĘDZENIE *OECOTHEA PRAECOX* (LOEW, 1862) (DIPTERA, HELEOMYZIDAE) ZE SŁOWACJI

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VLADIMÍR KOŠEL¹, ANDRZEJ J. WOŹNICA²

¹Nad lúčkami 53, 841 05 Bratislava, Slovak Republic, e-mail: kosel2@azet.sk

²Institute of Biology, University of Environmental Sciences, ul. Kozuchowska 5b
51-631 Wrocław, Poland, e-mail: Andrzej.woznica@upwr.edu.pl

ABSTRACT. *Oecothoa praecox* LOEW, 1862 (Diptera, Heleomyzidae) is a new species for the Slovak fauna. It was discovered in the Medzivrstvá jaskyňa cave, the Malé Karpaty Mts, 308 m a.s.l., 165 m long. The fly was widespread in the cave from euphotic up to aphotic zone in relative high number. Mating was observed in one case in February 2019. Eggs were not present in females. The taxon is supposed to live in Central Europe in caves permanently. The diagnostic characters are presented basing on analyzed male type-specimen and material available for studies. In the article, there are also summarized cave records of *Oecothoa fenestralis* (FALLÉN, 1820) in Slovakia from the years 1976-1993 and a discussion about the distribution of both species in European caves.

KEY WORDS: Heleomyzid flies, Oecothoini, Cave dwelling insects, *Oecothoa praecox*, *Oecothoa fenestralis*, faunistics, new records

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Oecothoa* HALIDAY IN CURTIS, 1837 (WOŹNICA & ZATWARNICKI, 1993) is represented by three species in Europe: *O. dubinini* GORODKOV, 1959 (WOŹNICA, 1993: 181), *Oecothoa fenestralis* (FALLÉN, 1820) with almost cosmopolitan distribution (besides of Afrotropical, Australian and Oriental regions), and *Oecothoa praecox* LOEW, 1862 with distribution in Europe - 13 countries according to Fauna Europaea (PAPE *et al.* 2015). In the neighborhood of Slovakia it is known from Czech Republic, Hungary and Ukraine and Poland. Its occurrence in Poland is doubtful (WOŹNICA 2018), because no specimens were

found in the museum collections and caves after the Second World War. Until now, it has not been recorded from Slovakia (DVOŘÁKOVÁ 2009). The first record in Slovakia originates from a cave in the south-west part of the country, in the Malé Karpaty Mts.

DESCRIPTION OF THE CAVE

The site of discovery of *Oecothea praecox* LOEW, 1862: Slovak Rep., Bratislava, Dúbravka env., Medzivrstvová jaskyňa cave, the Malé Karpaty Mts., DFS 7868, 308 m a.s.l., coordinates N48°10'30" E17°02'33".

The cave is 165 m long, its entrance is small (80 x 80 cm), artificially adapted as a shaft (Fig. 1). The cave has mostly low horizontal corridors with several blind branches. It lies in Sarmatian sandstones and limestones and was probably enlarged by exploitation of rock and sand (LEHOTSKÝ 1994). The cave lies in northern slope of the hill, surrounded by a deciduous forest with *Quercus*, *Carpinus* and *Acer*.

The temperature and air relative humidity in the cave (1. Febr., 2019) was from 3,0° C/ 89% a.h. at the 5th m, to 9,3° C/ 94% a.h. in the distance of 40 m from the entrance. The cave is relatively dry, and has mainly sandy bottom. There is a large amount of dry leaves on the floor up to 25 m from the entrance.

Fig. 1. The artificial entrance to the Medzivrstvová jaskyňa cave.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The cave was visited for the first time on 12. February, 2019. The flies were widespread in the cave from the 3rd m (euphotic zone) up to 40-50 m into dark (aphotic) zone. The sample contained 22♂♂ and 55♀♀. The highest number of flies was in the larger space 40 m from the entrance in aphotic zone.

The cave was repeatedly visited on 22 February, 2019. On this occasion, 29♂♂ and 25♀♀ were obtained. One pair of flies was observed „in copula“ in the aphotic zone. All females from both samples were without eggs in their abdomen. Average quantity of *O. praecox* on the cave walls was about 80 specimens on square meter, extremely high number was about 200 individuals.

Other parietal diptera in the cave from both data in February: *Culex pipens* 14♀♀, *Heleomyza modesta* 1♂, *Scoliocentra villosa* 3♂♂, 2♀♀ (A.J. WOŹNICA det.), Phoridae gen. sp. 2♀♀.

The collected material is preserved in pure ethanol and stored in plastic tubes.

In the nearby karst region near the village of Borinka (air distance about 20 km) where 6 caves were studied during several years, *O. praecox* was not found.

DISCUSSION

GORODKOV (1959; 1970) characterizes its occurrence „in caves“ and noted the similarity of male terminalia with *O. fenestralis*, except the cheek-eye ratio (ca. 1.0). It should be noted that in all collected specimens of *O. praecox* the first flagellomere is orange, eyes are much smaller than the size of gena (cheek-eye ratio is more than 1.0) (Fig. 2-3) and both wing cross-veins are only slightly dusted (Fig. 4). According to LERUTH (1934) it is a troglophile form, but nothing is known on its reproduction in caves. In spite of such characteristics, the taxon was found more often in artificial underground spaces (quarries and mines): in Belgium and Netherlands (LERUTH 1934) and in Ouest de France in two quarries (BEAUCOURNU & MATILE, 1963). From caves, it is known only from Germany (LERUTH, 1934). It seems to be lacking in caves in southern Europe from Portugal to Roumania.

With all probability the records of *Oecothoa praecox* from United Kingdom (<https://species.nbnatlas.org/species/NBNSYS0000029076>) needs verification (*unpublished results*), because the specimens were mostly recorded from small mammals burrows, while in Continental Europe a similar species *O. fenestralis* is a dominant taxon, and because of similarity of the male and female genitalia. The planned DNA analyses of *O. praecox* and *O. fenestralis* are important for verifying the status of both taxa, especially those specimens identified as *O. praecox* "and collected outside typical caverns.

Therefore the Medzivrstvá jaskyňa cave with the occurrence of *Oecothoa praecox*, can be considered as an extraordinary interesting site, and the following aim of the research will be to monitor the occurrence of the species in the cave all year round and also to find out reproduction possibilities.

Fig. 2. *Oecotoea praecox*, male, total habitus, lateral view.

Fig. 3. *Oecotoea praecox*, male, head in lateral view.

Fig 4. *Oecothea praecox*, male, wing in lateral view.

APPENDIX

Oecothea fenestralis (FALLÉN, 1820), a species related to *O. praecox* is predominantly a surface species, but sometimes can be found also in caves. In Slovakia, it was found in higher number of caves, but only sporadic. The first two data from caves in Slovakia were published by MARTINEK (1984).

RECORDS OF *OECOTHEA FENESTRALIS* FROM THE CAVES IN SLOVAKIA (FIG. 5)

The Slovak Karst Mts

Priepasť Brázda abyss (DFS 7488), (Silica env.) 1♀, 25 m deep below the entrance, 21. 6. 1981; Májkova jaskyňa cave (Silica env.), (DFS 7489), 1. 5. 1991, 1♂

The Slovenský raj Mts

Medvedia jaskyňa cave., Slovenský raj Mts, (DFS 7088), 22.2.1989, 25-30 m from the entrance, 1♀., 30.7.1989, 1♀, 15-20 m, disphot.

Vlčia jaskyňa cave, jask., Slovenský raj Mts, (DFS 7187), 23.9.1976, 10-15m, 1♀, euphotic part (MARTINEK, 1984)

Komíny jaskyňa cave, Slovenský raj Mts, (DFS 7187), 16.8.1988, 1♀.

Koniarova jaskyňa cave, Slovenský raj Mts, (DFS 7187), 19.8.1991, 1♀., 20-25 aphot.

Partizánska jaskyňa cave, Slovenský raj Mts, (DFS 7088), 24.6.1989, 1♀, 5-10 m, euphot.

Vojenská jaskyňa cave, Slovenský raj Mts, (DFS 7187), 20.8.1993, 1♀., 5-10 m, euphot.

The Revúcka vrchovina Mts

Veľká drienčanská jaskyňa cave, DFS 7586, 21.7.1990, 5-15 m, 1♂, euphotic part.

Malá drienčanská jaskyňa cave, DFS 7586, 31.7.1990, 1♀, euphotic part,

The Malé Karpaty Mts

Zbojnická jaskyňa cave, (DFS 7768), 326 m a.s.l., 15.7.1993, 1♀., 20-25 m, aphot. zone, 11.8.1993: 1♀., 15-20 m., disphot. zone.

Jaskyňa nad kamenolomom cave, Čachtický kras, Nové Mesto nad Váhom env., DFS 7272, 285 m a.s.l., 1♂ in soil trap, aphotic zone, 29.9.2016 (V. PAPÁČ leg., V. KOŠEL det.) (PAPÁČ 2018).

MATERIAL EXAMINED: 16♀♀, 3♂♂., occurrence in the months: 2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9.

LERUTH (1934) characterizes it as a „pholéophile“ species living in burrows of various mammals (e. g. *Oryctolagus*, *Mustela*, *Meles*). It was rarely found in caves: in Roumania, COLLART (1940) found a single specimen in a single cave, SÉGUY (1963) mentions it from 6 caves in the former Yugoslavia, BEAUCOURNU & MATILE (1963) - one cave in Ouest de France.

Fig. 5. The grid map of Slovakia with the occurrence of *Oecothea praecox* (black circle) and *Oecothea fenestralis* (empty circles).

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SÚHRN (SUMMARY IN SLOVAK)

Oecothea praecox LOEW, 1862, je novozistený druh muchy (Diptera, Heleomyzidae) v slovenskej faune. Charakterizuje sa ako druh viazaný na jaskynné a iné podzemné prostredie, napr. bane. Nálezy pochádzajú z Medzivrstvovej jaskyne v Devínskych Malých Karpatoch, je dlhá 165 m, vo výške 308 m. V 2 termínoch vo februári 2019 boli zistené obe pohlavia v pomerne vysokom počte v celom rozsahu jaskyne až do afotickej zóny. 1 pár bol pozorovaný v kopule. Možno prepokladať, že mucha žije v jaskyni trvalo. Je to zatiaľ jediná lokalita na Slovensku s týmto druhom. V článku je tiež vyhodnotený jaskynný výskyt príbuzného druhu *Oecothea fenestralis* (FALLÉN, 1820), ktorý nie je na jaskyne užšie viazaný a sporadicky sa vyskytuje v priebehu roka vo viacerých regiónoch Slovenska.

* **Editorial remarks:**

* Papers of the 35th volume of Dipteron are dedicated to the late AGNIESZKA DRABER-MOŃKO.